

URBAN-WASTE – 690452 – D3.8

URBAN-WASTE

Urban strategies for Waste Management in Tourist Cities

D3.8 – Staff Exchanges/Workshop Reports

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Abstract

D3.8 presents the activities and main lessons learnt from all staff exchanges organized within the URBAN-WASTE framework. In these exchanges, representatives from local authorities and tourism industry had the opportunity to share experiences and knowledge in terms of local innovative technologies and practices in waste management and prevention, which contributed to build capacities among staff from different pilot cases and to the potential replicability of such practices.

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List of abbreviations

ACR+	Association of Cities and Regions for Recycling and Sustainable Resource management
CE	Consulta Europa
WP	Work Package
D	Deliverable
EU	The European Union
EC	European Commission
EASME	European Agency for Small and Medium Enterprises

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1. Introduction

During the lifetime of the URBAN-WASTE project, a number of staff exchanges were organized between staff from local authorities and from the waste management industry. The main objective of the staff exchanges has been to provide a cross-country learning experience and sharing framework for innovative technologies in place that facilitate a solution or for exchange of ideas on how to tackle specific challenges faced by a given municipality with present technologies.

These activities were always organized in synergy with other project's mutual learning meetings in order to facilitate participation and reduce travel costs. At times, if it was considered that it would bring value to the staff involved and build capacities, the topics of the staff exchanges were in line with the topics chosen for the mutual learning meetings. These topics included:

- Gender mainstreaming in Waste Management - how to include and consider gender in all the aspects of waste management
- ICT solutions for tourism and waste
- Waste management planning with a special focus on tourism and tourism activities
- Implementing and monitoring waste management and prevention measures
- Food waste - how to face it?
- Bio-waste treatment on urban level: anaerobic digestion and composting
- Marine Litter: how to face it?
- Marketing measures and communicating good practices to different target groups
- Good practices in waste management as change makers in tourism
- Tourism, waste and heritage – how can they coexist?

On the other hand, in other occasions the staff exchanges' topics would not necessarily be related to the mutual learning topics but rather more inclined towards learning about local practices and technologies in place on waste prevention and management.

Each of the encounters facilitated a sharing environment where all participants could learn from each other and think about ways to replicate those initiatives or technologies at their own cities.

In total, 7 cities out of the 11 pilot cases hosted staff exchanges, excluding Syracuse, where the activity had to be cancelled due to weather conditions, Florence and Santander were no activities were organized, and Tenerife, where the kick-off meeting took place and no staff exchange was envisaged. Hence, the following were organized:

- Copenhagen (June 2017)
- Nicosia (October 2017)
- Nice (January 2018)
- Ponta Delgada (March 2018)
- Kavala (June 2018)
- Lisbon (December 2018)
- Dubrovnik (March 2019)

All exchanges had a general positive acceptance from participants, making it an attractive initiative to replicate from municipalities and other local authorities out of the consortium.

2. Staff exchange in Copenhagen

Date	2nd of June 2017
Participants	City of Copenhagen, Tuscany Region, Municipality of Kavala (DIAAMATH), Municipality of Lisbon and stakeholders.

Agenda

09:00	Welcome and introduction to program <i>Line Brogaard City of Copenhagen</i>
09:15	Waste sorting in households <i>Ane Kollerup - City of Copenhagen</i>
09:45	Short break
10:00	Household food waste prevention initiative in City of Copenhagen <i>Stine RK Knudsen - City of Copenhagen</i>
10:30	Plastic sorting plant in Copenhagen <i>Jonas Åbo Mortensen - City of Copenhagen</i>
11:00	Short break
11:15	Waste management in Kavala <i>Mrs Kyriaki Chioti-Prassa and Mr Alexis Michail - Kavala</i>
11:45	Introduction to the venues for visits
12:15	Lunch at the The Technical and Environmental Administration
13:15	Visits to sites in Copenhagen
	Hørgården - Local recycling station
	Vermlandsgade ARC - Recycling station

Waste sorting in households

The first lesson learned from the City of Copenhagen was related to the current waste sorting system in place for households in the city, emphasizing on how the City of Copenhagen applies and tests different tools to assist citizens in waste sorting at their households (*picture 1*).

Picture 1. Sorting containers for households in Copenhagen

Household food waste prevention initiative

Following the first part of the exchange, participants had the chance to learn from the initiatives that the City of Copenhagen adopts in order to tackle food waste and incentivize prevention. Particularly, a specific campaign was discussed, which was launched by the City with aims at motivating citizens to prevent food waste at households. This campaign was focused in transmitting some overarching messages such as:

- “Plan your dinner for tomorrow!”
- “Eat your leftovers!”
- “Eat me soon”- Shelf in the fridge
- Education on “Best before”- date and “At least good before”-date

Waste sorting facilities

Furthermore, participants visited a newly operating waste sorting plant in the city, which is characterized by automatically sorting metals and soft plastics as well as by counting on a NIR scanner for detecting and sorting different types of plastic (*picture 2*).

Picture 2. Waste sorting plant in Copenhagen

Following, some time was allocated for industry representatives from Kavala to present the state-of-the-art in waste management practices and technologies in their city and to exchange insights.

Local recycling stations

The last part of the activity involved the visits to two local recycling stations. From the first recycling station, *Hørgården*, participants learned that:

- The station is fenceless and therefore the atmosphere is open and welcoming.
- The citizens can deliver their recyclable waste materials in 11 fractions and swap used goods at the station.

- Social activities for the local citizens are arranged to make the recycling station an attractive place to come.
- A bike repair cafe is organized once a week, where citizens can get help by volunteers to fix their bikes.

In the second recycling station, located in Vermlandsgade (*picture 3*), participants learned that in 2016, 168.000 citizens and businesses delivered waste, where 13.000 tonnes of waste was sorted in 35 material fractions, 89 % was recycled, 8 % incinerated at the waste-to-energy plant, and only 3% landfilled. Major waste-types were construction and demolition waste, soil, bulky waste and hazardous waste. Furthermore, the station counts with swapping facilities available for citizens and businesses.

Picture 3. Vermlandsgade recycling station

3. Staff exchange in Nicosia

Date	20 th of October 2017
Participants	Municipality of Nicosia, City of Copenhagen, Cabildo de Tenerife and stakeholders

Agenda

08h45-09h00	Welcome to the participants from Nicosia pilot case
09h00-11h30	Visit the 'Integrated Solid Waste Management Facility' (IWMF) in Pendakomo, Limassol.
11h30-13h00	Visit Limassol Marina (commercial area) - Cleaning facilities and waste management practices, A. Tsouloftas @ Sons Ltd

Integrated Solid Waste Management Facility

The first visit of the staff exchange involved a visit to the integrated solid waste management facility (IWMF) in Pendakomo (*picture 4*). This infrastructure had been newly constructed and was not fully operational at that moment. Nevertheless, this facility had been constructed to serve the Limassol district and the surrounding communities. It comprises three different plants:

- Mechanical sorting
- Biological treatment
- Anaerobic digesters

Participants learned about the functioning of the facility in detail and the distribution of the plants. The visit consisted in an explanation through a presentation and a diagramme of the facility as well as a tour around each section. In particular, they learned about the anaerobic process that the facility would soon be able to generate and that will produce biogas from the organic fraction.

Picture 4. IWMF in Pendakomo, Nicosia

Limassol Marina

The second part of the staff exchange took place in Limassol Marina (picture 5), which is a popular commercial area with high tourism activity, where many restaurants, villas and other accommodation options can be found. Here participants could acquire a better understanding on how the waste is sorted and collected in this marina in particular. Specifically, how the different waste streams are sorted at source in recyclable paper, glass, PMD (plastic bottles, metal packaging and drink cartons) and residual waste (picture 6). The waste collection is carried out three times per week in the marina and cleaning operations in street and pedestrian areas takes place on a daily basis.

Picture 5. Limassol Marina overview

Picture 6. Waste sorting containers

Apart from acquiring a better understanding of how the waste collection and posterior treatment works in this marina, participants could experience first-hand one of the sustainability initiatives that the marina is undertaking and the tour around it was done with electric cars (picture 7).

Picture 7. Electric cars in Limassol Marina

4. Staff exchange in Nice

Date	26 th of January 2018
Participants	Métropole Nice Côte d'Azur (MNCA), Municipality of Ponta Delgada (FRCT), Municipality of Lisbon and stakeholders.

Agenda

14:00-17:00	Visit of organic recovery center with local reporter, local press, and Mr Leonelli – city of « Le Broc » (one of the 49 cities of MNCA)
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Organic waste recovery center

The staff exchange organized by MNCA consisted on a site visit the organic recovery plant of Le Broc (*picture 8*). In this plant, the main objective pursued is the reduction of weights and volume of waste and to obtain recoverable materials as compost and solid recovered fuel (SRF).

Picture 8. Participants of staff exchange in Nice

From the productive staff exchange, participants could learn from plenty of information and demonstrations provided about the organic recovery plant (*pictures 10 and 11*), such as:

- Built area = 12.000 m³ + 1.800 m² of biofilter
- Treatment capacity = 70.000 tonnes
- Investment cost = 29.000.000 €
- Exploitation = 70 €/tonne

Picture 10. Recovery plant

Picture 11. Matured compost produced

Material balance:

- Solid recovered Fuel = 15%
- Compost = 8%
- Ferrous = 2,5%
- Non-ferrous = 0,5%
- Paper and plastics = 12%
- Material waste(water) = 19%
- Inert = 3%
- Refusal = 40%

SRF characterization:

- Paper = 25,6 %
- Cardboard = 19,2 %
- Textile = 12,6 %
- Plastic = 26,2 %
- Combustible = 1,4 %
- Metal = 2,3 %
- Humidity rate= 17,4 %

5. Staff exchange in Ponta Delgada

Date	20 th of March 2018
Participants	Municipality of Ponta Delgada (FRCT), City of Santander, City of Copenhagen, Métropole Nice Côte d'Azur, DUNEA, Municipality of Lisbon, Municipality of Nicosia and stakeholders.

Agenda

13:30-14:30	Visit to Marina Atlântico Hotel – Sustainable good practices
14:30-17:30	Visit to the Ponta Delgada Municipality Waste Management System in nature tourism

Marina Atlântico – Sustainable hotel

During the staff exchange in Ponta Delgada, participants learned about many of the good practices that the Marina Atlântico Hotel carries out in order to be more sustainable in terms of energy efficiency and waste management and prevention. The hotel management explained how they acquired the environmental certification ISO 14001 and their registration on the Community System of Eco-management and Auditory (EMAS).

In particular, the main points of discussion were focused on:

- Substitution of disposable products;
- Measures to economize energy;
- Low water consumption in laundry;
- Increasing waste sorting (*picture 12*);
- Used cooking oil collection.

Picture 12. Waste sorting in hotel rooms

Ponta Delgada Waste Management System in nature tourism

The second visit involved an on-site explanation and demonstration on the waste management system in nature tourism in place for the Municipality of Ponta Delgada. This visit occurred in the *Sete Cidades Volcanic Complex* (picture 13), where participants were informed about the “eco-buildings” with “green” roofs from tourism infrastructures. Green roofs are, in essence, building roofs covered in vegetation over a waterproof membrane that offer a low visual impact on the environment among many other benefits, such as the self-regulation of the building’s temperature, maintaining cooler temperatures in summer and warmer in winter. In addition, the way that sustainable wood harvesting takes place and how its residues were treated was also one of the main points of discussion. Eventually, participants were introduced to the waste sorting system in place in the area, through the different waste bins allocated for each fraction.

Picture 13. Sete Cidades volcanic complex, Ponta Delgada

6. Staff exchange in Kavala

Date	27 th of June 2018
Participants	Municipality of Kavala (DIAAMATH), Cabildo de Tenerife, City of Santander, City of Copenhagen, Métropole Nice Côte d'Azur, DUNEA, Municipality of Lisbon, Municipality of Nicosia, Municipality of Syracuse and stakeholders.

Agenda

10.00 - 11.00	Recycling Site in Xanthi – Apostolos Demertzis, Hellenic Recycling Company
12.00 - 13.00	Measures for waste management during big events and festivals. The case of Cosmopolis Festival. Tour at Kavala Old City – Mr Anestis Tsouroukidis, Deputy Mayor of Kavala

Recycling Site in Xanthi

The staff exchange in Kavala offered a visit to a recycling site located in Xanthi and a tour around the old town to learn how the management of waste in the *Cosmopolis Festival* is carried out. However, due to weather conditions the tour was only partially done but extensive explanations and discussion took place.

The recycling site visited in Xanthi, one of the 32 recycling sites operated by the Hellenic Recovery Recycling Corporation (HERRCO) in Greece, started with a meeting where the Site Manager explained the operation of the recycling site and talked about the Hellenic Recovery Recycling Corporation. Some of the most relevant facts and lessons were that:

- The foundation of the Hellenic Recovery Recycling Corporation (HERRCO) took place in December of 2001, and was the result of an initiative taken among Greek companies active in packaging production and the trading of packaged goods, aiming to meet more effectively their legal obligation for the recycling of packaging waste deriving from their products through the self-administration of their funds within the framework of the National and European legislation.
- To respond to those requirements, HERRCO, in accordance with the law provisions, developed and implemented in Greece the Collective Alternative Management System – RECYCLING (CAMS – RECYCLING) by applying 6-year Operational Plans as approved by the competent authorities.
- HERRCO constitutes an exceptionally successful example of collaboration among the local packaging producers placing their products in the Greek market, the packaging importers and the Local Authorities of the country, who are legally bound for the collection of municipal waste.
- The Material Recovery Site in Xanthi serves 250.000 inhabitants and receives 7.000 tons of mixed recyclables, which are collected by a network of 4.200 recycling bins.

The meeting followed a tour visit around the facilities to have a better picture of the operations (pictures 14 and 15)

Picture 14. Manual sorting at the station

Picture 15. Compacted cardboard

The Cosmopolis Festival case

From the second activity of the day (picture 16), participants could learn from the case of the *Cosmopolis Festival* and the way waste is dealt with in an event with high affluence. This festival is organized in the Kavala old town, which comprises many touristic restaurants, and many cultural events taking place every year.

Cosmopolis Festival is one of the biggest events taking place every year. It involves the celebration of civilizations, which is organized in the old town at the *Panagia Peninsula* with “narrow alleys with the traditional houses and stores fill with dances, music and little children’s voices”. Being a multicultural city since the dawn of its history, Kavala, is the ideal representative of *otherness* and multiculturalism.

The festival was first held in 2000 and, from 2002 to 2009, it is an annual reference point in the cultural life of the city of Kavala and the wider region. *Comopolis* involves:

- CosmoConcerts
- CosmoDances
- CosmoTastes
- CosmoEvents
- CosmoKids

Picture 16. Waste tour around Kavala's oldtown

One of the challenges faced relates to the space availability for waste bins, taking into consideration that the streets are very narrow, and cars can hardly pass. Therefore, the Municipality of Kavala has installed a pilot underground waste bin (*picture 17*) that replace at least 5 of the normal bins. The plan is to expand the installation of such bins in the whole old city area.

Picture 17. Underground waste bins in Kavala

7. Staff exchange in Lisbon

Date	29 th of November 2018
Participants	Municipality of Lisbon, Municipality of Ponta Delgada (FRCT), City of Santander, Municipality of Syracuse, Tuscany Region, DUNEA, Municipality of Nicosia and stakeholders

Agenda

14:30-16:30	Visit to Bordalo II street art and atelier
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Bordalo II, conscious street art and atelier

In the staff exchange organized in Lisbon, municipal representatives and stakeholders from the hotel industry learned from a local street artist that collects and upcycles plastic waste and transforms it into art. This initiative does not only have a powerful awareness raising component for waste prevention, but it also grants a second use to plastic waste.

Artur Bordalo, aka *Bordalo II*, born in Lisbon in 1987, paints on the street since "very young age", being the public space where he feels most at ease, in his own words.

With a strong view about sustainability, ecological and social awareness, he develops his works of art under the philosophy of "one man's waste is another man's treasure", creating, recreating or assembling using end-of-life materials. Last year, *Bordalo II* had several of his works exhibited in Lisbon.

The exhibition "Attero" (waste in Latin), with new pieces that are an extension of the works that he has created in the street from recovered waste in several places of the world.

Because of the exhibition he created three pieces in the street, which are part of the "Big Trash Animals" series: a fox (*picture 18*), a frog (*picture 19*) and a monkey (*picture 20*), which are a part of a series of artworks that aims to draw attention to a current problem involving waste production, materials that are not reused, pollution and its effect on the planet. The artist idea is to represent nature itself, in this case animals, out of materials that are responsible for its destruction.

Picture 18. The Fox

Picture 19. The Frog

These works are done with end-of-life materials: the majority found in wastelands, abandoned factories or randomly and some are obtained from companies that are going through a recycling process, such as damaged bumpers, burnt waste containers, tires and appliances.

During the visit to *Bordalo II* atelier participants had the opportunity to see the artist at work, and to discuss more about his ideas, motivations and inspiration.

Through this creative initiative, participants could learn how the Municipality of Lisbon supports creative initiatives that intend to raise awareness on a common problematic: the waste over-production.

Picture 20. The Monkey

8. Staff exchange in Dubrovnik

Date	14 th of March 2019
Participants	DUNEA, Tuscany Region, City of Copenhagen, Nicosia Municipality, Cabildo de Tenerife, City of Santander, Ibiza Municipality, Porto Municipality and stakeholders.

Agenda

09:00 – 10:00	City centre tour – Impact of tourism and waste management (meeting point Pile Gate)
10:00 – 10:30	Bus transfer to Konavle Municipality
10:30 – 11:30	Visit to Konavoski Dvori – Sustainable restaurant and cultural heritage promoter (Ljuta, Konavle Municipality)
11:30 – 13:00	Visit to Seoska kuća Čilipi - Novaković Household, Golden Orange winner for 2018 (Čilipi, Konavle Municipality)

Impact of tourism and waste management in Dubrovnik's old town

The first activity involved a tour around the old town of Dubrovnik, where participants learned about how it became to be an UNESCO World Heritage Site, the tourism pressures that currently faces and the waste management challenges raised as a consequence.

Konavoski Dvori – Sustainable restaurant and cultural heritage promoter

On the second site visit, participants had the opportunity to learn from a sustainable restaurant and cultural heritage promoter, *Konavoski Dvori* (pictures 21 and 22). Some of the most important facts and lessons learnt were:

- It became the first green restaurant in Croatia with received non-repayable EU funds; the use of renewable energy sources (sun, water, wind) will allow it to operate year-round, which was not possible before. All of this will additionally raise the awareness of guests and the public of the significance of this place as a component of the Konavle region's cultural and natural heritage and the role of Konavoski Dvori in the tourism promotion of the wider Dubrovnik region and Croatia as a whole. The initial vision of *Konavoski Dvori* as a green restaurant is successfully continuing. By implementing and co-financing this project, this restaurant has once more pushed forward the

boundaries of its operations in the hospitality industry and, with the help of the European Union and its funds, demonstrated that the key to success is smart and sustainable resource management.

- Croatian Environmental Protection and Energy Ministry has recognized the importance of the project to transform the Konavoski Dvori, housed in a mill next to the Ljuta Stream, into a green restaurant, and through the European Regional Development Fund has approved co-financing for Esculap-Teo's project on the 'Konavoski Dvori Restaurant Energy Supply Renewal' which will renovate the building's envelope and replace the existing, obsolete technical fixtures with new, more energy efficient installations, and introduce new systems that use renewable sources of energy.
- The purpose of the project is to reduce energy consumption by 52.79% (in comparison to energy delivered prior to project implementation) and increase the share of renewable sources of energy in gross energy consumption by 27,371.08 kWh, and hence increasing efficient energy use in the service sector (tourism, retail). This project will, thereby, increase the competitive edge of the entire Croatian economy.

Picture 21. Konavoski Dvori restaurant

Picture 22. Presentations at the restaurant

Seoska kuća Čilipi - Novaković Household

The third activity of the staff exchange constituted a site visit to *Seoska kuća Čilipi - Novaković* household (picture 23), where participants learned that:

- *Seoska kuća Čilipi* is a farmhouse, a household maintained by family Novaković. It is located in the village Čilipi (17 km from Dubrovnik), suitable for organized trips presenting the life in the countryside in the past and present, giving accent to sustainable development in rural areas, with special focus on environment and nature protection on the basis of traditional agriculture and cultural site, as a best practice for sustainable waste management.
- Participants had an opportunity to visit sustainable garden, agricultural goods and a barn for livestock, a small ethno-museum which consists of three small arches representing a part of history of Konavle region and a tavern with a wine cellar and a selling room with exhibited handmade souvenirs. The Country house is partly several hundred years old, and some parts have been added over

centuries to the present state. The whole construction was badly damaged in the Homeland war in 1991 and restored later.

- For the year of 2018, this household received a 1st place, winner for the Golden Orange award which criteria was ecological production of all products, preservation and originality of cultural and natural heritage.

Picture 23. Seoska kuća Čilipi - Novaković household

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